

Engineering of Textile Coloration

Md. Anowar Hossain

Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Permanent Campus: Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh
(enqr.anowar@yahoo.com)

Keynote of Thesis

This report denotes the laboratory techniques of textile coloration, textile dyes applications and method design as per color requirements to perform as color engineers in textile dyeing and finishing industry.

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain (2015), Engineering of Textile Coloration, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Permanent Campus: Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh

A Thesis Submitted for the Degree of Bachelor of Science in Engineering in 2010, Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Permanent Campus: Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh

Author profile edited in 2023

Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID)

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

Uniform Resource Locator (URL) of LinkedIn Profile

www.linkedin.com/in/enqr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Research gate profile

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Enqr-Md-Hossain>

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

PhD Researcher (Technical Textiles), Thesis-final part

*School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)*

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTEchin Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering

City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Consultant (Textile coloration, Defence textiles, Technical textiles)

Office: 512.01.12, 25, Dawson Street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Australia

enqr.anowar@yahoo.com +61 452209738, +8801788396264

Lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former chief executive officer, Bangladesh textile and fashion, Uttara, Dhaka

Former product developer and coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.

Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying and Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka

Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT TO CITY UNIVERSITY UNIVERSITY

I acknowledge Engr. Ismat Zerín for her academic supervision. I felicitate to **Dr. Engr. Saiful Islam, Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering** for his cordial support and continuous guidance throughout my long journey in City University & **Textile Engineering Senior Project**

I am giving special thanks all of my respected teacher of City University who are cordially helped me to achieve textile knowledge. Specially, my textile engineering knowledge is the reflection of following highly experienced teachers.

1. Dr. Engr. Saifur Rahman, Associate Professor
2. Dr. Arun kanti Guha, Assistant Professor
3. Engr. Rafiqur Rashid, Associate Professor
4. Engr. Rina Khanum, Assistant Profesor
5. Engr. Amirul Islam, Lecturer
6. Engr. Rokonuzzaman, Lecturer
7. Engr. Bithi Choudhury, Lecturer
8. Engr. Abdullahil Kafi, Lecturer
9. Engr. Rishad Riyaan, Lecturer
10. Engr. Jenifar Amman, Lecturer
11. Engr. Lutfur Rahman (Faruk), Lecturer
12. Engr. Sujit Shaha, Lecturer
13. Engr. Kamruzzaman, Lecturer

14. Engr. Azhar Ali, Lecturer
15. Engr. Arifuzzaman, Lecturer
First Batch, City University

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT TO NIAGARA ACKNOWLEDGEMENT TO NIAGARA TEXTILES LTD. TEXTILES LTD.

I specially congratulate to **Engr. Md. Abraruzzaman Diamond, General Manager of Niagara textiles Ltd** for his permission to conduct my **Textile Engineering Senior Project** without which it would be uncompleted.

I also sincerely thanks to the following personalities from which I have taken lots of support to prepare this present report during my **Textile Engineering Senior Project**

1. Engr. Abu Bakar Siddique, Dyeing Manager.
2. Engr. Toriqul Islam, Knitting Manager.
3. Engr. Saydur Rahman, Electrical Manager.
4. Engr. Zafor, Asst. Dyeing Manager
5. Engr. Monju Rahman, Senior Production Officer, Dyeing
6. Engr. Sohanur Rahman, Senior Production Officer, Dyeing
7. Engr. Khalid faisal, Production Officer, Dyeing
8. Engr. Arifur Rahman, Production Officer, Dyeing
9. Engr. Shimul kumar, Production Officer, Dyeing
10. Engr. Abdullah, Production Officer, Dyeing
11. Engr. Nazmul Shakib, R & D Officer
12. Engr. Asaduzzaman, Production Officer, Dyeing
13. Engr. Zafor Ahmed, Production Officer, Knitting
14. Engr. Monsi Abdus Salam, Production Officer, knitting
15. Engr. Mahfuz, First Batch, City University.
16. Engr. Mihir Ranjon Das, First Batch, City university

Introduction

Reactive dyes are extensively used for dyeing and printing cellulosic materials and blends containing cellulosic portion. This is the reason behind the fact that researches on synthesis and development of reactive dyes, improvement of their application possibilities and procedures has been practicing mostly by dyers, chemists and engineers. It has also been found that the dyeing properties mean the applicability, technology, permanency etc. and structure of reactive dyes is its molecular structure. Method of application and permanency of dyeing are much dependent on the composition of the reactive dyes, more directly we can say that on the functional group attached with the reactive dyes. Several reactive dye functional groups have been synthesized, their chemistry has been understood and behavior on application and permanency on the substrate has been discussed in terms of exhaustion and fixation. These two properties in case of reactive dyeing define the suitability, compatibility, permanence, economy etc of dyeing.

The functional or reactive group or groups attached with the reactive dye molecule have direct effect on the exhaustion and fixation of dyes with the cellulosic substrates. The other chemicals and dye bath conditions used in dyeing process also have their effect in exhaustion and fixation but these are not properties of dyestuffs or only assist to improve and fixation.

In this project we are supposed to find out the effect of functional reactive groups on the exhaustion and fixation behavior of reactive dyes on cotton substrate in terms of physical and chemical analysis.

Objectives:

The project has the following objectives:

*To find out and compare the effect of dyeing parameters (Conc. of electrolyte, temperature, time, M: L ratio) on dyeing cotton with the reactive dyes.

- *To locate the optimum condition for exhaustion and fixation for dyeing on cotton with the reactive dyes for different dyeing parameters.
- *To select the suitable dyeing parameters for standard dyeing of cotton with reactive dye.

Beside these insightful objectives the project also targeted to reach the following side objectives

- *To minimize the wastage of dyes.
- *To simplify the dyeing condition.
- *To point out the exact time of fixation of dye stuff for desirable shade.

Application aspects of this project:

Dyes are one of the most important raw materials of a dyeing industry. As cotton dyed mostly in our country by reactive dyes, these are conveniently used and consumption of reactive dyes of different functional groups is highest in dyeing industries. So, judgment of applicability, behavior, performance and permanence of reactive dyes is of most interest not only to dyeing industries but also to dye sellers and students of apprentices who are studying wet processing. In following paragraphs, we will discuss the aspects of this project:

Application aspects to dye seller:

Dye sellers are supposed to match the trichromate for combination dyeing of textile goods. It has been found that dyes of same functional groups are the perfect trichromate. The reason is that, they have same or nearly same temperature point of exhaustion and fixation. By this project we will establish this phenomenon by experimentation. So, discussing the behavior of exhaustion and fixation dye sellers can suggest the dyeing industries to use the best combination.

Application aspects to the dyeing industries:

Without considering the reactive functional groups of reactive dyes trichromatic combination, shade matching, dyeing intermediate addition of particular shade becomes complicated. For this reason, understanding the behavior of reactive functional group is essential for dyers in dyeing industries.

Application aspects to students and apprentices:

Study of behavior of functional groups of reactive dyes is essential for students and apprentices of wet processing. The only window to understand dyes such as reactive dyes is to study the functional groups. The chemistry of the dye is totally depended on the functional group of the dye and functional group determines the exhaustion and fixation behavior of reactive dyes. The application of dyes to substrate also guides by the exhaustion and fixation behavior of the dyes and students must be aware of such projects

Description of Cotton Fibre

Why Cotton fibre

Reactive dyes can be applied to cotton, silk and polyamine fibers successfully. But in this project, applied the reactive dyes to cotton fibers substrate. The reason of taking cotton fibre is too much logical from the consumption point of view of this fibre. Cotton is extensively used natural fibre reaction manner of cotton fibre with reactive dyes is well defined and the on of reactive dyes synthesized for cotton dyeing is large. Moreover, reactive dye is mainly used for cotton fibre dyeing and silk or polyamide fibres dyed with acid dyes.

Fibre criteria:

Macroscopic structure: Cotton fibres are the seed hairs of the plant *Gossypium*. They are usually of white in colour although some varieties have been bred to incorporate a natural colour. Each fibre is formed by the elongation of a single cell from the surface of the seed.

Microscopic structure: Under a microscope a cotton fibre appears as a very fine, regular fibre, looking like a twisted ribbon or a collapsed and twisted tube. These twists are called convolutions.

Chemical Structure of cotton fibre:

Chemical constitution:

- Cellulose-85.8%
- Oil and Wax-0.5%
- Proteins, Pectoses and coloring matter-5%
- Mineral matter-1%
- Moisture-8.5

Fibre Properties

Physical properties:

Specific gravity	1.52 to 1.55.
Moisture regain	8.5.
Strength	Tenacity: Dry 3.5 g/d, Dry x1.11
Elasticity	Low
Breaking extension	5-7% and recovery- 52 at 5%
Stiffness	57-60 g/d.
Resiliency	Low

Abrasion resistance	Medium
Dimensional stability	Medium

Chemical properties:

Effect of acid: Cotton is weakened and destroyed by the effect of acids; hydrolyse the glucoside linkage of oxygen atom. Concentrated nitric acid, for short time, causes some shrinkage and increase and increase strength and disability.

Effect alkali: Normally resistant, when boiled in presence of O_2 , oxycellulose form. Treatment with 20% $NaOH$ increase strength and dye ability. Liquid ammonias treatment increase strength, elongation, etc. Both of solution is used as mercerizing liquor.

Effect of bleach: All kinds of bleaching agents have its action on cotton. $NaOCl$ and Na -perborate are common. H_2O_2 is least harmful.

Effect of organic solvent: Cotton is resistant to organic solvent. So dry wash is possible.

Effect of heat: Conducting ironing temperature $-150^\circ C$. Decompose at $240^\circ C$. Ignition temperature $390^\circ C$.

Effect of sunlight: Affected by infrared cause deteriorates colour becomes yellow.

Dye ability: Azoic, Direct, reactive, sulphur and vat dyes are applicable to cotton substrates.

Attack by moth: NO.

Attack by mildew: Untreated not starches and gums increase activity.

Description Of Reactive dyes

Definition:

The dye that possess a reactive group as its constituent which is capable of reacting chemically with a substrate (cotton, wool etc.) to form a dye substrate covalent bond is known as reactive dye.

Here the reactive dye present in the dye molecule act as an integral component of the fibre polymer after dyeing in a favorable condition. Mainly the reaction occurs in an alkaline condition (PH>10). The covalent bond is formed between the dye molecule and –OH group of cellulose or NH₂ (amino group of polyamide or wool fibre). The general reaction between dye molecules and the fibers are as below:

Where, D= Dye part

Example: Procion Yellow R

Cibacron Turquoise Blue G

Reactive dyes contain at least a reactive group in its constituent. This reactive group reacts with the fibre polymer and formed covalent bond in an alkaline condition. This can be illustrated by following reaction of procion dye which possesses Dychloro Triazinil reactive group with cellulose. For this reason these dyes are called reactive dyes.

The major developments of reactive dyes

Reactive dyes are occurred organic substance wick are water soluable.

These dyes will react with cellulose through covalent bonds under certain condition of pH, temperature, solution and time.

We see the following development on reactive dyes

- April 1956, ICI introduced procin R dyes. These dyes are halogen derivatives.
- June, 1957, CIBA introduces CibacronR dyes, a new range of reactive dyes. This new range is also halogen derivatives.
- In 1957, Hoechst introduces vinyl sulphoneR dyes, the first reactive dyes based on vinyl sulphone derivatives.

General structure of reactive dye:

The general structure of reactive dye is as below:

Here,

Dye part or color producing chromogen part

D=

linking part

B=b

Reactive group bearing part

G=

Reactive group.

X=

Example: Procion yellow

In the reactive dyes the dye part can be of direct, acid, disperse or premetallize etc dyes. $-\text{NH}-$, $-\text{NH}_2$, $-\text{N}-\text{R}$ groups bridges between dye part and the reactive group bearing part.

The hetero cyclic rings such as triazine groups are the reactive group bearing part and halogen or activated vinyl compounds are the reactive groups.

Classification of reactive dyes:

Reactive dyes can be classified in various ways as below:

On the Basis of Reactive group:

On the basis of reactive group present in the dyestuff, reactive dyes are classified into types:

1. Hetero cyclic compounds containing nitrogen with halogen derivatives.
2. Activated vinyl compounds.

1. Hetero cyclic compounds containing nitrogen with halogen derivatives:

These are further classified into three types as below:

- I. Triazine group.
- II. Pyrimidine derivatives.
- III. Quinonoline derivatives.

2. Activated vinyl compounds:

These are also three types as follows:

- i) Vinyl sulphone:
D- $\text{SO}_2 - \text{CH}_2 - \text{CH}_2 -$

Example: Remazol

- ii) Vinyl acrylamide:
D- NH- COO- CH₂ - CH₂ -
Example: Primazine
- iii) Vinyl sulphonamides:
D- SO₂- NH -CH₂ - CH₂ -
Example: Levafix

B) On the Basis of Reactivity:

On the basis of reactivity reactive dyes are of three types they are

1) Lower reactive dyes :

Reactivity of that dye is low. So highly alkaline environment required for the fixation of those dyes with substrate. Here Ph is maintained 12-12.5 by using NaOH in bath: Example Cibacron T.

2) Medium reactive dyes:

These are medium reactive dyes. Here P^H is maintained 11-12 by using Na₂ CO₃ (Soda ash) in dye bath. Example: Levafix E, Remazol.

3) Higher reactive dyes:

These dyes are highly reactive. So fixations of these dyes are easy and lower alkaline medium is kept. Here P^H is maintained 10-11 by using NaHCO₃ in dye bath. Example: Procion Mx. Drimarene KL`R.

On the basis of dyeing temperature and method:

They are of three types:

1) Cold brand:

These types of dyes are highly reactive as they possess highly reactive group in their constituent. So dyeing of these dyes can be done in lower temperature i.e. 32-60⁰ C. Example: Procion Mx. Levafix E etc.

2) Medium brand:

These types of dyes contain reactive group of moderate reactivity. So dyeing is done in higher temperature than that of cold brand. Here temperature is kept between 60⁰ C to 71⁰ C.

3) Hot brand:

These types of dyes contain reactive groups of least reactivity. So high temperature is required for dyeing i.e. 72-93⁰ C temperature is kept for dyeing. Example: Procion H, Cibacron T etc. are hot brand dyes.

History of Reactive dyes:

The discovery in 1954 of the concept of reactive dyes carrying dichlorotriazinyl groups led to the reappraisal and rapid exploitation of this area. The first systemic study of nucleophilic attack at a double bond activated by a sulphonyl group was made by two Harvard chemists in 1935 and, from this academic beginning, has grown a commercially important reactive dye class.

On the occasion of 100 years celebration of synthetic dye manufacturing, two chemists of ICI company (UK) named Stephen and Rattee tried to manufacture a new dyestuff. Thus they succeeded to invent a new dye in 1956, which was named REACTIVE DYE. This was manufactured for dyeing cellulosic fibers. The first three reactive dyes were PROCION YELLOW R, PROCION BRILLIANT RED 2B and PROCION BLUE 3G. For this effort they were awarded gold medal of the society of dyes and colorists for the year 1960. These dyes came to our country in mid 60s and became very popular during 80s.

Much of the research effort on reactive dyes since the mid 1960s has been concerned with the design of dyes containing two reactive groups. Initially so called homo bi functional reactive dyes where both groups are identical were developed and commercialized and such products offered improvements in fixation efficiency. However in 1979 interest in the bi functional concept was considerably intensified by the launch of the first range of hetero bi functional dyes. Such dyes have two non identical groups. During mid 1980s attention was once again directed towards homo bi functional types with both bis vinylsulphonyl and bis monochlorotriazinyl based products receiving further evolution.

Properties of Reactive Dyes:

Physical/ chemical Properties:

Chemical Structure	Mostly triazinyl and vinyl sulfone derivatives of monoazo and acid chlorid compounds, characteristically small and simple molecular structures. Anionic in electrostatic nature.
Physical state	Used as solutions. Depends on base compounds.
Molecular Weight	Low generally, ranges 69-211g/mole. The higher the MW the more costly the dyeing because more dye has to be used to produce the same shade.
Water Solubility	Generally very good. Sometimes modified to lower solubility.
Hydrolysis	Dye-fiber bond is hydrolyzed by strong acids or bases the more reactive dichloro and trichloro phirmidine are especially hydrolysis prone. During the application of conventional reactive dyes. 15-40% of the dye is hydrolyzed.
Spectra	Have very bright shades owing to their very narrow and high absorption bands which result from their simple structures.
Bonding Types	Covalent bond to fiber substrate. Vinyl sulfones form amino bonds with silk, wool and ether bonds to cellulose. Acid cholrides form amide bonds with wool and ester bonds with cellulosic's.

Application Properties of Reactive Dyes:

Leveling	Very good.
Exhaustion	Good
Migration	Extremely good
Acid fastness	Dye-fiber is hydrolyzed
Alkali fastness	Fair to good. Index 3-5.
Light fastness	Very good. Index 5-6.
Coloring fastness	Limited.
Wash fastness	Very good. Index 4-5.
Perspiration fastness	Good. Index 4-5.

Useful colors	Full range of colors from extremely light to heavy darks. No fluorescent shades.
Rate of dyeing	Very rapid.
Dyeing process	Exhaust.
After treatment	Soaping and rinsing to remove hydrolyzed dyestuffs.

The Reactive system:

Reactive groups:

Following are the reactive groups found in reactive dyes:

Name	General structure
Mono chloro-s-triazine dyes	
Dichloro-s-triazinyl dyes	

Trichloro Pyrimidyl dyes.	
Tri fluoro pyrimidyl dyes	
Fluro chloro pyrimidyl dyes	
Pyrimidyl dyes	
Phthalazine dyes	
Bifunctional dyes Monochloro triazine - Vinyl sulphone dyes	
Vinyl sulphone dyes	$DSO_2 - CH = CH_2$
Acrylamide dyes	$D - NH - CO - CH = CH_2$

Characteristics of reactive group of reactive dye:

The characteristics of reactive group of reactive dyes are mentioned below:

- 1) The reactive system doesn't contribute to the color of the dye which is determined by the chromogenic part of the reactive dye.
- 2) The reactivity of the reactive dyes determined by the presence of reactive groups such as halogens, vinyl sulphone, vinyl-acrylamide and vinyl sulphonamides. Reactivity also depends on the no of N atom on the reactive group bearing heterocyclic part.
- 3) The fluoride radical has the least reactivity as its bond energy 102 Kcal/gm. So drastic conditions are required for bringing about the reaction.

- 4) Iodide radicals are most reactive among the halides. But Iodo and Bromo reactive dyes are so reactive that they hydrolysed very rapidly in aqueous solutions.
- 5) The chloro group is preferred commercially as its price is low and its reactivity lies midway between that of other groups.
- 6) The reactivity of the dye may be considerably increased by attaching chloro group to monochlorotriazine ring. Thus, the dichloro reactive dyes are known as cold dyeing reactive dyes.
- 7) The reactivity of the monochlorotriazine dyes may further increased by replacing the chloro group by a quaternary ammonium radical.
- 8) When the chloro group is replaced by the sulphonate ($-SO_3 Na$) group both solubility and reactivity of the dye are increased.
- 9) When thio sulphate group ($-S-SO_3 Na$) is attached affinity decreases and become unsuitable for application in exhaustion method. But suitable for pad-cold fixation technique.
- 10) The molecular weight of reactive dyes varies between 69 and 211. The molecular weight of the reactive systems contiguities the cost of the dye.

- 12) By replacing one of the nitrogen atoms of the triazine by a carbon atom the reactivity of the reactive group decreases.

Reaction manner of dye and cellulose:

The reaction manner of the dye and cellulose are mentioned below:

- 1) Hydroxyl group of cotton polymer takes part in reaction with reactive group of dye.
- 2) Reactive group of dye react preferably with the hydroxyl group of cellulose than that of water.
- 3) The activation energy of dye-water reaction is 16.4-26.2 Kcal/gm and that of dye cellulose is 9.2-15.8 Kcal/gm.
- 4) Higher the activation energy, slower the reaction.
- 5) The reaction with water and dye takes place.
- 6) The strength of covalent bond formed between cellulose polymer and reactive group is more than hydrogen bonding, vander walls force of attraction and metal co-ordination bonds.
- 7) Extreme acidic and alkaline condition should be avoidable otherwise hydrolysis will take place resulting bond breakage and poor wash fastness.

Criteria of cellulose for attaching reactive dyes:

The chemical structure of cellulose macro molecule is given below:

In cellulose macro molecule glucose units are linked through oxygen bridges formed between C1 position of glucose and C4 position of adjacent glucose unit. Each glucose unit contains one primary hydroxyl group at C6 position and two at second hydroxyl group at $-CHOH$ position at C2 and C3

Positions. Now the following things are considered:

Primary hydroxyl group is supposed to be more acidic than C3 hydroxyl group under suitable alkaline condition and hence more reactive.

C2 hydroxyl group is more active while the additional hydroxyl group of C4 position is the least reactive.

The reaction between reactive group and cellulose takes place predominantly with primary hydroxyl group and that with secondary hydroxyl group to some extent.

Longer carbon chain lowers the rate of reaction.

In case of monochlorotriaziny dyes this reaction takes place 15 times more frequently with C6 hydroxyl group at C2 position.

The reactive rates of some compounds are given below:

Compound	Structure	Reactive rate
Water	H-OH	1.0
Iso-propanol	CH ₃ -CH-OH-CH ₃	0.7
Ethanol	CH ₃ -CH ₂ -OH	7.4
Methanol	CH ₃ -OH	12.3
Glucose	N C ₆ O ₅ H ₁₀	5.5

So, from the above discussion it is obvious that secondary hydroxyl group is the least reactive while the primary one is the most reactive.

Different Types of Dyes Used:

Chemical Name	COUNTRYNAME	Brand Name of dyestuff
DY-STAR	GERMANY	Remazol Golden Yellow RGB
		Remazol Deep Black RGB
		Remazol Deep Black GWF Gran
		Remazol Red RGB Gran
		Remazol Turquoise Blue G133%
		Remazol Brilliant Blue R Spec
		Remazol Brilliant Blue BB 133% Gran
		Remazol Ultra Carmine RGB
		Remazol Ultra Carmine RGB GR
		Levafix Rubine CA Gran
		Levafix Red CA Gran
		Levafix Olive CA Gran
		Levafix Fast Red CA Gran
		Levafix Brillant Red E-4BA Gran
		Dianix Navy CC
		Dianix Turquoise S-BG
IMPOCOLOR	GERMANY	Imcozin Blue E-NR
		Imcozin Blue V-CR 150%
		Imcozin Brilliant Red V-F3B
		Imcozin Brilliant Yellow V-4GL
		Imcozin Yellow E-3R 150%
BENZEMA	SWITZER LAND	Bezaktive Blue S-GLD 150
		Bezaktive Yellow S-3R 150
		Bezaktive Red S-3B 150
CLARIANT	SWITZER LAND	Drimarene Yellow K-4G Cdg
HUNTSMAN	SWITZER LAND	Terasil Red W-4BS
		Terasil Nevy W-RS
		Novacron Red FN-R-01
		Novacron Yellow F-4G
JIHUA	CHINA	Starfix Black B 150%
		Starfix Red EP 150%
SUMIFIX	JAPAN	Sumifix Supra Blue E-XF
		Sumifix Supra Yellow E-XF

SUN COLOR	KOREA	Sunfix Navy Blue MF-D
CHEMICAL NAME	BRAND NAME	COUNTRY NAME
Wetting agent	Feloston NOF	Germany
Levelling agent	A-41	China
Anti-creasing agent	Kapavon CL	Germany
Per Oxide Stabilizer	Kapazon H-53	Germany
	CBB	
	Rucorit Wez	
Caustic	Caustic	China
Soda Ash	Soda Ash	China
H ₂ O ₂	H ₂ O ₂	China+Korea
Optical Brightening Agent	Uvitex-BMA	Switzerland
	Uvitex-BHV	
	Uvitex-BBT	
	Syno White 4Bk	Korea
H ₂ O ₂ Killer	Kapatex-PKS	Germany
Acetic Acid	Acetic Acid	India
Sequestering Agent	Securon-540	China
	CS	
	Polyclean-SP	India
Enzyme	Bio-ACE	China
	Biopolish-B41	Srilanka
Electrolyte / Salt	Sodium Sulphate	India
	Anhydrose	
	Glubar Salt	
Detergent	Rukozen-WBL	Germany
	Diwet PIUS	India
Soaping Agent	Rukozen-NZA	Germany
	Dekol ISN	China
	Cyclonon XEW	
Softener	Nerosoft-JS(an-ionic)	China
	Nerosoft-NI(non-ionic)	
	Purrustol-IMA	Germany
Fixing Agent	Sandofix-EC	Germany

	Protan FCE-375	
--	----------------	--

Methods & Measurements (Dyeing of cotton fabric with reactive dyes)

Quality of water used:

water is a vital raw material in wet processing. The water for dye house should possess the following qualities or maintain the following standards:

Minimum Standard	Permissible Concentration
Color	Colorless
Smell	Odourless
pH value	7 (neutral)
Hardness	Less than 5 ⁰ Dh
Dissolved solids	Less than 1 gm/litre
Solid deposits	Less than 50 gm/litre
Organic Substances	Less than 20 gm/litre
Inorganic salt	<500 gm/litre
Iron	<0.1 gm/litre
Copper	<0.005 gm/litre
Nitrate	<50 gm/litre
Nitrite	<5 gm/litre

LAB DIP DEVELOPMENT

DEFINITION

LAB dip development means the sample which is dyed according to buyer's requirements (similar shade and so on). Depending on lab dip development sample dyeing and bulk production the dyeing planning done.

OBJECTIVE OF LAB DIP

The main objectives in LAB dip are as follows.

- ❖ To calculate the recipe for sample dyeing.
- ❖ To compare dyed sample with swatch by light Box or Spectroflash.
- ❖ To calculate revise recipe for sample dyeing.
- ❖ Finally approved Lab Dip(Grade: A B C).

Work flow chart of dyeing lab:

Send to floor for bulk production

Available Stock Solutions:

- Red – 0.1%, 0.5%, 1.0%, 2.0% (very common)
- Yellow – 0.1%, 0.5%, 1.0%, 2.0% (very common)
- Blue - 0.1%, 0.5%, 1.0%, 2.0% (very common).

Preparation:

- To prepare 0.1% Stock solution, it is necessary to mix 0.1 g dye and 100 cc water.
- To prepare 0.5% Stock solution, 0.5 g dye stuff is mixed with 100 cc water.
- To prepare 1.0% & 2.0% Stock solution similar procedure is followed.
- To prepare 10% Stock solution of Soda ash, 10 g Soda is mixed with 100 cc water.

AMOUNT OF DYES SELECTION:

$$\text{Amount of dyes} = \frac{\text{Sample weight} * \text{Shade}\%}{\text{Stock Solution}} \text{ cc}$$

$$\text{Amount of salt} = \frac{\text{Fabric weight} * \text{Liquor ratio} * \text{gm/l}}{1000} \text{ gm}$$

SAMPLE CALCULATION FOR 0.5% SHADE

- ⇒ Sample wt. = 5 mg
- ⇒ Material liquor ratio = 1: 10
- ⇒ Total liquor (5 × 10) = 50 cc

$$\Rightarrow \text{Dye solution required} = \frac{5 \times 0.5\%}{1\%} = 2.5 \text{ cc}$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{Salt solution required} = \frac{50 \times 25}{20 \times 10} = 6.25 \text{ cc}$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{Soda ash solution required} = \frac{50 \times 10}{20 \times 10} = 2.5 \text{ cc}$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{Water required} \{50 - (2.5 + 6.25 + 2.5)\} = 38.75 \text{ cc}$$

Pippet selection:

Shade %	The following pippets are selected according to shade perchantage-	Pippet (ml)
(.001-.1)%		.10
(.11 to.20)%		.20
(.21 to.50)%		.50
(.51 to 1.00)%		1.00
(1.1 to 2.00)%		2.00
(2.1 to 5)%		5.00
(5.1 to 10)%		10.00

M/C SPECIFICATION OF USING DYEING MACHINE

M/c no: 01

Number of Using Bikar :16

M/c name: MIR Dyeing Machine

Rotation Speed: 5-60 RPM

Origin: TAIWAN

Heating range: Room temp to 140C

Type: Dyeing m/c

Weight: 90kg

M/c no: 02

M/c name: digiWash I NX
Brand name Paramount
Origin: INDIA
Type: washing (for color fastness)

Fig: digiWash I NX

Scouring and Bleaching:

Objects of scouring:

1. To remove the natural added impurities like oil wax gums fatty materials as completely as possible.
2. To get a clean and even fabric suitable for the next process ie; dyeing, printing, finishing etc.
3. To increase the absorbency of the fabric ie; to make the fabric hydrophilic, so that it can absorb dye molecules, water and other chemicals easily.
4. To make the fabric ready for bleaching ie; for removing natural coloring matters.

Objects of Bleaching:

1. To ensure a permanent white colour in fabric.
2. To ensure that the fabric does not undergo any physical or chemical damage due to bleaching like loss of tensile strength.
3. To increase absorbency for further operation.
4. Clariant one bath scouring and bleaching (exhaust) was done.

Estimating effect:

Absorbency:

Drop test was done for the estimation of absorbency. This test is a very easy test and is commonly used in industries. It gives result very fast.

Test:

In a pipette a solution of 0.1% direct red was taken and is dropped on the fabric sample. Then the absorption of the colored drop is observed visually. Then two things are measured and taken into consideration:

1. The time taken to absorb one drop of solution.
2. The shape of the absorbed area on the drop.

Result:

1. The standard time taken for the absorption of one drop of solution is 0.5-0.8 second or it should be within 1 second.
2. And if the spot is circular but less area of spreading it means even but incomplete scouring.

If the spot is circular and bigger in radius, it means even and completes scouring.

If the spot size is irregular, it means uneven scouring.

Whiteness:

When a fabric is bleached, its light reflecting capacity increases. The reflectance of a bleached fabric is measured by spectrophotometer.

Acceptable range of reflectance: 84%-86% (very common).

A range of 90-92% reflectance is also possible in bleaching at high temperature (120°C). In high temperature we can get high range of reflectance but high temperature bleaching is risky.

Evaluation:

Absorbency: Good

Degree of Whiteness: CIE White 77.96%

Fabric pH: 7

Dyeing

In this project we dyed the scoured bleached cotton fabric of same lot with dyes containing same reactive groups and of medium and dark shade. For dyeing with different dyestuffs we choose the best dyeing temperature and time duration prescribed by the dye manufacturer. Because it is not possible to find out the best suitable recipe and dyeing condition for a particular type of dyestuff in such a project. Following we discuss different methods and their recipe of dyeing with dyeing condition.

Dyeing Auxiliaries

Different auxiliaries used in reactive dyeing

Albafluid C : Ladiquest 1097-U has the ability to form complexes with polyvalent metal ions in aqueous solution so that their Characteristics are not apparent.

Dispersing agent:- Ladiquest 1097-U facilitates the dispersion of particles in a dispersing (usually water) and increases the stability of the dispersion.

Protective colloid:- This property closely depends on the dispersing power. The addition of Ladiquest 1097-U protects colloiddally dispersed particles from agglomeration. It is foam free agent, low electrolyte content, electrolyte resistance, stable to oxidizing and reducing agents and to acid and bases.

The recommended quantity of Ladiquest 1097- U for water softening is 0.2 gm/liter per ⁰ German hardness.

It has been found that 0.3- 0.5 ml/liter in dye bath will give a level and uniform dyeing effect. With dye impregnation processes. 1 ml/litre recommended in order to obtain good results.

In dyeing we have used 1 gm/liter Ladiquest 1097-U.

Drimagen E-2R as Levelling agent:

Drimagen E-2R controls the exhaustion of reactive dyes during the adsorption phase. It's pH regulating effect ensures uniform fixation of the dyes during the alkali addition. It Sequesters hardness forming substances found in the works water, on the goods or even in electrolytes and permits improvement of dyeing reproducibility.

Density: - 1.22 at 20⁰ C

Storage ability: - Good between 10-50⁰ C

Stability: - To salts, acids, alkali, hard water.

Foaming behavior: - Foams Slightly.

It is recommended to use 1-2 gm/liter Drimagen E2R Liquid.

In dyeing we have used 1 gm/liter Drimagen E2R Liquid.

Process variability: - Same amount of chemicals are used for all groups of reactive dyes.

After Wash:

In this process we practiced two types of after wash. Firstly for fixation samples we wash properly with the following wash procedure. And for exhausted we consider that the dye taken up by the fibre fixed and adsorbed on the substrate surface. For this reason we only squeeze the dyed sample without washing them.

Different after wash:

i. Hot wash:

Treat the fabric at 80⁰ C for 10 minutes.

It is done for removing alkali and unfixed dyes.

ii. Neutralization:

After giving the hot wash there may remain the alkali. So neutralization is done by Acetic Acid at 0.5 g/liter to maintain the pH.

iii. Soap wash:

Soap wash is done at 80⁰ C for 5 min with Avlon As (Soaping agent). It is used at 1 g/l and 1.5 g/l respectively for medium and dark shade.

The dyes which do not create bond with fibre i.e.; unfixed are cleaned by soap wash. So the permanency of brightness is increased.

Effect of after wash:

In case of reactive dyeing 50-60% of dye may hydrolyse. The amount may be reduced for high fixation dyes but normally for hot brand dyes this may be increased. To remove the unfixed dyes from the fibre surface we have to practice a long after wash procedure. The washing procedure is lengthy but unavoidable. For proper wash Fastness we should go through these procedures.

Analysis Of Dyeing Parameters

Dyeing parameters:

The key factors which affect all steps of dyeing process mostly exhaustion and fixation rate during dyeing is called dyeing parameters.

Various key factors are as follows:

- Inherent substantivity of dyestuff
- Liquor ratio
- Dye bath temperature
- Salt Concentration
- Leveling properties of dyestuff
- Chemical reactivity of dyestuff
- pH of dye bath

pH of dye bath:

The role of alkali is to cause acidic dissociation of some of the hydroxyl group in the cellulose and it is the cellulosate (cell-O-) that react with the dye.

i.e alkali is responsible for reaction between dye and fibre or for fixation of dyes in the fibre

$\text{Cell-OH} + \text{HO}^- = \text{Cell-O}^- + \text{water}$

- Reactive dyes have little affinity for cotton as long as the pH is neutral or slightly acid.
- Alkali must also be present for the dye stuff to become reactive.
- As alkali is added, the dye has more affinity for the cotton.
- As the temperature increases, the dye stuff completes the reaction with the cotton in the presence of alkali.

Temperature:

The affinity of the dye for the fibre decreases with increase in temperature and the rate of hydrolysis of the dye increases and adversely affect the fixation. The rate of diffusion of the dye in the fibre increases with increased temperature.

Electrolyte:

The fixation can be increased by exhausting the dye bath by adding salt prior to fixation. The amount of salt required to produce adequate exhaustion decreases with decreasing liquor ratio.

Salt remarkably reduces the electro negativity of fibre surface. For this reason, anionic reactive dye shows its affinity for cellulosic fibre and increase the exhaustion rate.

Standard application of salt and soda with various types of dyeing chemical:

Name of dyestuff: Novacorn FN/S/W

	<0.1	>0.1-0.25	>0.25-0.5	>0.5-1	>1-2.0	>2.0-3.0	>3-4	>4-5	>5
Salt (g/l)	10	15	20	30	40	50	60	70	80
Mixed alkali method									
Soda ash	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Caustic Flakes(g/l)	0.5	0.5	0.5	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.5	1.5	1.5
Soda ash method									
Soda ash	8	10	12	14	16	18	20	20	20

Name of dyestuff: NOVACRON FN/S/W%

	<0.1	>0.1-0.25	>0.25-0.5	>0.5-1	>1-2.0	>2.0-3.0	>3-4	>4-5	>5
Salt (g/l)	7	10	14	21	28	35	42	50	80
Soda(g/l)	10	12	14	16	18	20	20	20	20

Name of dyestuff: LEAVAFIX:

PERCENT	0-0.1	0.1-0.5	0.5-1.0	1-2	2-3	3-5	5.0+++
SALT (g/l)	15	15-20	20-35	35-50	50-60	60-80	80-++

SODA (g/l)	5	5-7	7-10	10-13	13-15	15-20	20-++
---------------	---	-----	------	-------	-------	-------	-------

Name of dyestuff: REMAZOLE

PERCENT	0-0.1	0.1-0.5	0.5-1.0	1.0-2.0	2.0-3.0	3.0-5.0	5.0-++
SALT (g/l)	20	20-25	25-40	40-50	50-60	60-80	80-++
SODA (g/l)	5	5-7	7-10	10-13	13-15	15-20	20-++

Name of dyestuff: REMAZOLE TURQUISE:

PERCENT	0-0.1	0.1-0.5	0.5-1.0	1.0-2.0	2.0-3.0	3.0-5.0	5.0-++
SALT (g/l)	20	20-25	25-40	40-50	50-60	60-80	80-++
SODA (g/l)	3	3	3-5	5-8	8-10	10-12	12-++

Time:

With the time the dye from the liquor transferred into the fibre core and the shade become deep to deeper. When the time goes on the dye fixed into the fabric. Time is an important parameter because it plays a vital role into the depth of the shade. So get the desirable colour there is a specific time limitation.

Liquor Ratio:

M: L ratio is an important parameter for dyeing cotton fabric with dyes in exhaust method. With decreased liquor ratio, both exhaustion and fixation take place to increased extent. The rate of fixation of most dyes is not significantly affected. As the liquor ratio is decreased, the effectiveness of increasing salt addition also decreases. For vary small range of M:L ratio may creat uneven dyeing, fabric tangling etc. From the practical we can say std. M:L ratio is essential for better performance.

Some Important terms

Exhaustion:

In exhaust dyeing, all the material contacts all the dye liquor and the fibers absorb the dyes. The dye concentration in the bath therefore gradually decreases. The degree of dyebath exhaustion as a function of time decreases the rate and extent of the dyeing process. For a single dye, the exhaustion is defined as the mass of dye taken by the material divided by the total initial mass of dye in the bath. But for a bath constant volume:

$$\% \text{Exhaustion} = (C_0 - C_s) / C_0 \times 100$$

Where C_0 and C_s are the concentrations of dye in the dye bath initially and sometime during the process, respectively.

Dyeing equilibrium:

The gradual transfer of dye bath from the dyeing solution and in the fibre eventually leads to a point at which the distribution of the dye between the fibre and the solution is kept constant in time or can be considered more or less constant. The overall system is in equilibrium. The equilibrium which is reached depends on the working conditions of the dye in the solution.

Substantivity:

Substantivity is the attraction between dye and fibre whereby the dye is selectively absorbed by the fibre and the bath becomes less concentrated. The term is originally derived from the substantive dye which can be equated with the uptake of a dye or an auxiliary i.e. with its ability to uptake a dye from a liquid medium onto a textile substrate and to set. A dye must have affinity to a textile substrate so that it can show Substantivity. It depends on PH of liquor, temperature, liquor ratio, type of fibre, concentration of added electrolytes, etc.

Migration:

Migration is the movement of a particle i.e. dye, pigment, cross linking agent, etc due to an electric field from one part of textile material to another according to the concentrations of that substance (from higher to lower concentration area)

Diffusion:

Diffusion is the movement of a particle, i.e the dye owing to a concentration gradient (a difference in the amount of material from one place to another)

as can occur in a dye bath from the bath to the fibre diffusion layer called convective diffusion, from absorbed state to the inner polymer of the fibre structure naming molecular diffusion.

Fixation:

After all washing and after treatment process dye molecules become physically or chemically bonded with the fibre polymer so that dye becomes fixed with the material by a heat treatment process. This is called fixation.

Practical Analysis of Dyeing Parameter:

Name of parameter: Electrolyte-Salt

Dyed Sample	Dyeing Recipe
Dyed sample is not attached here	Bodactive.BR.Red.CFG = 0.128 Bodactive.Red.CFR.SFL = 0.78 BodactiveScorCf.HC = 0.008 21/15
	Bodactive.BR.Red.CFG = 0.128 Bodactive.Red.CFR.SFL = 0.78 BodactiveScorCf.HC = 0.008 30/15

	<p>Bodactive.BR.Red.CFG = 0.128 Bodactive.Red.CFR.SFL = 0.78 BodactiveScorCf.HC = 0.008</p> <p>60/15</p>
--	---

Name of parameter: Electrolyte-SODA

Sample	Dyeing Recipe
Dyed sample is not attached here	<p>Bodactive.BR.Red.CFG = 0.128 Bodactive.Red.CFR.SFL = 0.78 BodactiveScorCf.HC = 0.008</p> <p>30/10.5</p>
	<p>Bodactive.BR.Red.CFG = 0.128 Bodactive.Red.CFR.SFL = 0.78 BodactiveScorCf.HC = 0.008</p> <p>30/15</p>

	<p>Bodactive.BR.Red.CFG = 0.128 Bodactive.Red.CFR.SFL = 0.78 BodactiveScorCf.HC = 0.008</p> <p>30/30</p>
--	---

Dyeing Parameter: Material: Liquor Ratio

Sample	Dyeing Recipe
	<p>M:L = 1:6</p> <p>KTR-R-RGB = 0.74 % KTR-Y-HB = 0.82 % SOLA-R-SP2B = 3.8 % 80/20</p>
	<p>M:L = 1:10</p> <p>KTR-R-RGB = 0.74 % KTR-Y-HB = 0.82 % SOLA-R-SP2B = 3.8 % 80/20</p>

	<p>M:L = 1:16</p> <p>KTR-R-RGB = 0.74 % KTR-Y-HB = 0.82 % SOLA-R-SP2B = 3.8 % 80/20</p>
--	--

Dyeing parameter: pH

Sample	Dyeing Recipe
	<p>M: L = 1: 10</p> <p>Dychofix Yellow-3RXF = 2.60% Remazol Red-RR =0.15% Dychofix Navy Blue-GG =1.96% 80/20 pH = 5</p>
	<p>M:L = 1:10</p> <p>Dychofix Yellow-3RXF = 2.60% Remazol Red-RR =0.15% Dychofix Navy Blue-GG =1.96% 80/20 pH = 10</p>

	<p>M:L = 1:10</p> <p>Dychofix Yellow-3RXF = 2.60%</p> <p>Remazol Red-RR = 0.15%</p> <p>Dychofix Navy Blue-GG = 1.96%</p> <p>80/20</p> <p>pH = 14</p>

Dyeing parameter: Temperature

Sample	Dyeing Recipe
	<p>M: L = 1: 10</p> <p>Remazol Terquise blue g = 1%</p> <p>Soda = 15%</p> <p>Salt = 60%</p> <p>Temperature: 60</p>

	<p>M: L = 1: 10</p> <p>Remazol Terquise blue g = 1% Soda = 15% Salt = 60% Temperature: 70</p>
	<p>M: L = 1: 10</p> <p>Remazol Terquise blue g = 1% Soda = 15% Salt = 60% Temperature: 90</p>

Dyeing parameter: Time

Sample	Dyeing Recipe
	<p>M: L = 1: 10</p> <p>Remazol Terquise blue g = 1% Soda = 15% Salt = 60% Time: 60 min</p>

	M: L = 1: 10 Remazol Terquise blue g = 1% Soda = 15% Salt = 60% Time: 80 min
	M: L = 1: 10 Remazol Terquise blue g = 1% Soda = 15% Salt = 60% Time: 100 min

Measurements of shade difference due to change in parameters:

Different methods:

Shade difference of cotton sample dyed with reactive dyes in various changing parameters can be measured by different methods. Few methods are given below:

- Visual method
- By colorimeter
- By spectrophotometer

The accuracy of these three methods lies in the underlying technique and principle of measurements. The visual method is least accurate as it only can be used to compare the depth of the colour of different dyes on substrate by experienced person and approximately can only be done. The spectrometric method of measuring colour strength is based upon the reflectance of coloured sample and measurements of opaque, translucent and liquid surfaces is available from which exhaustion and fixation can be measured.

Visual method:

Depth of shade of dyed sample can be compared with one another visually. The visual method only can compare shade depth but cannot measure with any values. So its results can be used for approximation not for a definite decision. This method also has no scientific support.

By spectrophotometer:

Spectrophotometer uses the reflectance of reflections from a coloured object throughout the visible spectrum. It results a curve showing the reflectance values at different point of wavelength of visible spectrum.

By using Spectrophotometer first recipe was formulated for different parameters and dyes. Then after dyeing was measured the shade difference between samples and standard accordingly we got the pass-fail result by using the spectrophotometer.

Common dyeing faults analyzed in dyeing production

unit for different dyebath with their remedies

1. Uneven dyeing:

Causes:

- Uneven pretreatment (uneven scouring & bleaching).
- Improper color dosing.
- Using dyes of high fixation property.
- Uneven heat-setting in case of synthetic fibers.
- Lack of control on dyeing m/c

Remedies:

- By ensuring even pretreatment.
- By ensuring even heat-setting in case of synthetic fibers.
- Proper dosing of dyes and chemicals.
- Proper controlling of dyeing m/c

2. Batch to Batch Shade variation:

Causes:

- Fluctuation of Temperature.
- Improper dosing time of dyes & chemicals.
- Batch to batch weight variation of dyes and chemicals.
- Dyes lot variation.
- Improper reel speed, pump speed, liquor ratio.

- Improper pretreatment.

Remedies:

- Use standard dyes and chemicals.
- Maintain the same liquor ratio.
- Follow the standard pretreatment procedure.
- Maintain the same dyeing cycle.
- Identical dyeing procedure should be followed for the same depth of the Shade.
- Make sure that the operators add the right bulk chemicals at the same time and temperature in the process.
- The pH, hardness and sodium carbonate content of supply water should check daily.

3. Roll to roll variation or Meter to Meter variation:

Causes:

- Poor migration property of dyes.
- Improper dyes solubility.
- Hardness of water.
- Faulty m/c speed, etc

Remedies:

Use standard dyes and chemicals.

Proper m/c speed.

Use of soft water

Crease mark:

Causes:

- Poor opening of the fabric rope
- Shock cooling of synthetic material
- If pump pressure & reel speed is not equal
- Due to high speed m/c running

Remedies:

- maintaining proper reel speed & pump speed.
- Lower rate rising and cooling the temperature
- Reducing the m/c load
- Higher liquor ratio

Dye spot:

Causes:

- Improper Dissolving of dye particle in bath.
- Improper Dissolving of caustic soda particle in bath.

Remedies:

- By proper dissolving of dyes & chemicals

- By passing the dissolved dyestuff through a fine stainless steel mesh strainer, so that the large un-dissolved particles are removed

Wrinkle mark:

Causes:

- Poor opening of the fabric rope
- Shock cooling of synthetic material
- High temperature entanglement of the fabric

Remedies:

- Maintaining proper reel speed & pump speed.
- Lower rate rising and cooling the temperature
- Higher liquor ratio

Softener Mark:

Causes:

- Improper mixing of the Softener.
- Improper running time of the fabric during application of softener.
- Entanglement of the fabric during application of softener

Remedies:

- Maintaining proper reel speed & pump speed.
- Proper Mixing of the softener before addition.
- Prevent the entanglement of the fabric during application of softener

Conclusion

For the assessment of result of the effect of dyeing parameter (Alkali, M:L ratio, PH, Electrolyte, Time, Temperature) on dyeing of cotton with reactive dye. In this report, assess the shade without the use of spectrophotometer to determine the lightness or deepness of the shade from the standard shade when the parameters are changed. It was not able to include reflectance curve due to some technical problems of spectrophotometer.

References

Hossain, M. A. (2009). *Basic Knowledge of Wet Processing Technology*, ISBN-978-984-35-2885-8, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh (Vol. 1-4). Rupok Publications.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844857>